

GEOTECHNICAL BIM FOR QUANTITY TAKE-OFF IN TUNNELING STRUCTURES WITH GROUND DEFORMATION

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Supervisor

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Abstract

The implementation of Building Information Modelling (BIM) methodology in the infrastructure field, awakes several questions in different aspects. One of them is about the workflow for the quantity take-off in tunnelling structures where the New Austrian Tunneling Method (NATM) is used very often for the excavation process. The estimation of quantities for the excavation and primary support in tunnels requires to consider the ground deformation, meaning that geotechnical processes should be integrated with BIM processes. The author explores the current development of BIM standards for infrastructure and tunnelling structures through bibliographical research and will explore geotechnical tools for BIM in tunnelling structures, geological and geotechnical modelling, and the interoperability capabilities between modelling tools and geotechnical tools. Using the Second Track Tunnel Divača – Koper (2TDK) project as a case study, the author proposes a workflow for the quantity take-off in NATM Tunnels considering the ground deformation integrating the geotechnical analysis as a part of the BIM process. It proposes a geological excavation model as a solution for information management during the excavation and construction phases.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/2020-CristianRincon-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/zpKdb8GEaTQ>

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